

1 **Effect of melatonin supplementation to a cytoprotective medium on post-thawed**
2 ***Brycon orbignyanus* sperm quality preserved during different freezing times**

3

4 Priscila C. Palhares ^a, Isadora de L. Assis ^b, José Gilmar da Silva Souza ^b, Thales de
5 Souza França ^b, Renata Catão Egger ^b, Daniella Aparecida de Jesus Paula ^b, Luis David
6 Solis Murgas ^b *.

7

8 ^a Departamento de Zootecnia, IF do Sudeste de MG, Rio Pomba, Minas Gerais, Brasil
9 Dept. Animal Science, Federal University of Lavras, UFLA, Lavras, Minas Gerais,
10 37200-000, Brazil

11 ^b Departamento de Medicina Veterinária, Universidade Federal de Lavras (UFLA),
12 Lavras, Minas Gerais, Brasil

13

14 This is the accepted manuscript of the article:

15 Palhares, P. C., Assis, I. L., Souza, J. G. S., França, T. S., Egger, R. C., Paula, D. A. J., &
16 Murgas, L. D. S. (2020). Effect of melatonin supplementation to a cytoprotective medium
17 on post-thawed *Brycon orbignyanus* sperm quality preserved during different freezing
18 times. *Cryobiology*, 96, 159–165. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cryobiol.2020.07.002>

19

20

21

22

23 *Corresponding author:

24 Dr. Luis David Solis Murgas, Departamento de Medicina Veterinária, Universidade
25 Federal de Lavras (UFLA). Caixa Postal: 3037, CEP: 37200-14 000, Lavras, Minas
26 Gerais, Brasil. E-mail: ismurgas@ufla.br

27 **Abstract**

28 The aim of the present study is to verify the viability of frozen *B. orbignyana* sperm cells
29 after freezing with dilution media containing different concentrations of the melatonin
30 and after different freezing times. Semen from 15 males was collected and pooled as five
31 pools from three random animals. Oocytes (100) from three females separately were used
32 for fertilization. There were three treatments: (C) 10% methylglycol (MG) + 5% extender
33 Beltsville thawing solution (BTS); (M1) 5% BTS + 10% MG + 1 mmol L⁻¹ melatonin;
34 and (M2) 10% MG + 5% BTS + 2 mmol L⁻¹ melatonin. Sperm samples were diluted in
35 media at a final proportion of 1:4 [125 µl sperm (25% V/V) + 337.5 µl BTS (65% V/V)
36 + 37.5 µl MG (10% V/V)]. Melatonin was added at final solution. Three Dry shipper
37 freezing times were used: T1 (15 minutes), T2 (12 hours) and T3 (24 hours). The samples
38 were transferred, stored in a cryobank and thawed in a water bath at 60°C for 5 s and
39 evaluated concerning viability, morphology and fertilization rate. *B. orbignyana* semen
40 frozen in M2 presented the highest fertilization rate ($8.40 \pm 2.54\%$). The highest vitality
41 ($85.2 \pm 2.8\%$), motility ($64.63 \pm 8.3\%$), motility duration ($84.22 \pm 11.4s$) and progressive
42 motility ($17.01 \pm 1.2\%$) rates were maintained for M2. The highest number of altered
43 cells was observed in C ($57.4 \pm 5.9\%$). Melatonin at 2 mmol L⁻¹ associated with the
44 cryoprotectant methylglycol in cryopreservation could be used to improve a cryobank for
45 endangered *Brycon orbignyana* populations.

46 **Keywords:** CASA; sperm motility; cryopreservation; antioxidant; dry shipper.

47

48 1 INTRODUCTION

49 The piracanjuba (*Brycon orbignyanus* Valenciennes, 1849), as it is popularly known, it is
50 a freshwater fish species native to the Paraná and Uruguay rivers basins. It migrates long
51 distances to reproduce, going up the river between September and October, and spawning
52 between November and January [27]. It is considered an important species in South
53 America, due to its meat quality and aggressive behavior in sport and professional fishing
54 [21,39]. This species has displayed a marked population decline and has become extinct
55 in almost the entire length of its basin of origin and is now categorized as endangered by
56 the Red Book of Brazilian Endangered Fauna [2].

57 The species clearly is unable to survive in reservoirs or river stretches with flow regimes
58 regulated by hydroelectric dams [27]. The creation of this insurmountable barrier to their
59 migration blocks fish movement to the upper parts of the basin, increasing juvenile
60 mortality due to spawning outside suitable conditions for their development [10,50].
61 Different conservation strategies are required in order to mitigate migratory fish
62 populations decline, such as the creation of animal germplasm banks, through semen
63 freezing for later availability [20].

64 In addition to comprising a technique for long-term gamete storage, semen
65 cryopreservation is a technique that can increase fish reproductive period flexibility and
66 operationalization and assisted reproduction programs [8]. Freezing fish semen methods
67 have progressed in recent years, due to numerous applications, for example, through
68 genetic improvement and breeding management programs in aquaculture, in studies
69 with applying different biotechnologies using model fish species (preservation of
70 transgenic or mutant lines) and in the cryobanking of genetic resources of threatened
71 species [5]. It is important to note that in Brazil, a country with a significantly diverse
72 freshwater fish fauna, a germplasm repository was created for several important species,
73 including *Brycon orbignyanus* [32]. However, as it can generate about 50% of cell
74 damage due to freezing and thawing, cryopreservation success is partial. These damages
75 may occur due to the formation of intracellular ice crystals, the toxicity of the solutions
76 used in the process or sperm cell sensitivity to oxidative stress due to reactive oxygen
77 species (ROS) [8,33]

78 Among several freezing fish semen methods, freezing in cylinders containing nitrogen
79 vapor (Dry-Shippers) is the most noteworthy, guaranteeing cooling rates between 10 and
80 60 °C min⁻¹ [22], although it is considered a relatively new technique due
81 to recent literature assessments [55]. This method consists in maintaining the sperm cells

82 at this temperature for a certain amount of time until transfer to cryobanks. Some studies
83 have developed freezing methods based on various exposure times, ranging from 10 min
84 to 48 hr prior to freezing in liquid nitrogen containers [14,23,54]. However, scarce reports
85 on the effect of this “pre-freezing” on semen freezing of native Brazilian fish species are
86 available.

87 Sperm cells are very sensitive to the oxidative stress that occurs during the freezing
88 process, and ROS are formed due to the low amounts of antioxidants and the high
89 concentration of polyunsaturated fatty acids in the plasma membrane [7]. High ROS
90 concentrations may impair certain cellular functions, such as sperm motility [28].

91 Sperm and seminal plasma contain enzymes and antioxidants responsible for the removal
92 of free radicals. However, this may not be sufficient for cellular protection [47].
93 Melatonin is an antioxidant capable of sequestering highly reactive free radicals,
94 neutralizing the hydroxyl radical. It is an effective direct and indirect antioxidant, as it
95 detoxifies the highly reactive hydroxyl radical and neutralizes other toxic species
96 including singlet oxygen, hydrogen peroxide, nitric oxide and peroxyxynitrite anion, and
97 stimulates various antioxidant enzymes [46].

98 The addition of antioxidants to the freezing medium protects sperm from free radical
99 damage [29]. In this regard, melatonin effects were recently evaluated concerning
100 *Prochilodus lineatus* semen freezing, and no significant differences were found between
101 melatonin-containing cryoprotectant solutions and the control solution [4]. However,
102 these findings may be species-specific and should be tested for different fish species. The
103 efficiency of this molecule in the preservation of frozen semen from other animal species
104 has been demonstrated [3,24,44,51].

105 In this context, the aim of this study was to verify the viability of frozen *B. orbignyanus*
106 sperm cells in enriched media containing different melatonin concentrations and after
107 different freezing times in a liquid nitrogen vapor canister.

108

109 **2 MATERIALS AND METHODS**

110 **2.1 Site, animals and pre-assay period**

111 All experimental procedures were performed according to the Federal University of
112 Lavras ethics committee rules (process n° 039/13) and were carried out from October
113 2016 to February 2017 at the Volta Hydroelectric Power Plant Fish Station Big. Fifteen
114 adult piracanjuba males ($1,160 \pm 120$ g) and five adult females ($1,320 \pm 260$ g) were
115 selected and maintained in running water concrete tanks at 28 to 30 °C. Breeders

116 presenting secondary sexual characteristics, such as the presence of reddish genital
117 orifices and bulging cellomatic cavity (females) and semen release under cellomatic wall
118 compression (males) were selected.

119 The reproduction induction method was performed by animal hypophysation, according
120 to the methodology adopted at the CEMIG Volta Grande Fish Farming Station. Females
121 received three intramuscular injections of carp pituitary extract (CPE; Argent Chemical
122 Laboratory, Redmond, Washington, USA) at 0.25, 0.5 and 5.0 mg kg⁻¹ body weight, with
123 a 12 h interval between doses, while males received one intramuscular injection of carp
124 pituitary extract (5.0 mg kg⁻¹ body weight) at the same time as the second female dose.
125 After 5 h at 27 °C, the urogenital papilla was carefully dried, sperm from each male was
126 hand-stripped directly into test tubes and oocytes from females were hand- stripped into
127 plastic beakers.

128

129 **2.2 Semen collection**

130 Semen was collected by placing the fish on a flat surface with their eyes covered by a
131 damp cloth. The urogenital papilla was dried with a paper towel and the semen was then
132 extruded by means of manual celomatic wall massage in the cranial-caudal direction. The
133 semen was collected in graded test tubes and placed in a Styrofoam box containing ice
134 bars and maintained in these conditions until freezing (approximately 5 to 10 minutes).

135 Immediately, each sperm sample was subjectively evaluated concerning sperm motility
136 and motility duration after activation in 40 µL of 1% NaHCO₃, using a light microscope
137 (Eclipse E200, Nikon, Tokyo, Japan) at a X 200 magnification. Any observed sperm
138 motility was considered premature induction caused by urine or water contamination
139 [12,14,18,21,30,42]. A 5 µL semen aliquot from each male was deposited on a
140 histological glass slide and observed under an optical microscope. Only samples
141 displaying motility over 80% were used for subsequent analyses. Five pools containing
142 semen from three randomly selected animals were used for each sample pool.

143

144 **2.3 Semen cryopreservation**

145 The tested extender was the commercial Beltsville Thawing Solution (BTS[®], Minitüb,
146 Tiefenbach/Landshut, Germany), previously described by Maria et al. [30] prepared with
147 deionized water at 5% (4.0% glucose, 0.63% sodium citrate, 0.13% EDTA, 0.13%
148 NaHCO₃, 0.08% KCl, 0.02% gentamycin sulfate). Methylglycol 10% [CH₃O(CH₂)₂OH];
149 Vetec Química Fina Ltda., Duque de Caxias, RJ, Brazil) was used as the cryoprotectant

150 agent (CPA). All sperm samples were individually diluted in the 7 freezing media at a
151 final ratio of 1:4 [125 μ L sperm (25% V/V) + 337.5 μ L BTS (65% V/V) + 37.5 μ L
152 methylglycol (10% V/V)]. Melatonin (N-acetyl-5-methoxytryptamine; molecular weight
153 232.3, Natrol LLC, Chatswoth, California, USA) was dissolved in the total solution added
154 to the extender and methylglycol, yielding two different final concentrations [4].
155 Melatonin was added at a final concentration of 1 mmol L⁻¹ and 2 mmol L⁻¹ and calculated
156 for the total solution (Sperm + Extender + CPA) for each straw (500 μ L). The osmolality
157 of all solutions was tested and, when necessary, solutions were adjusted to 320 mOsm
158 with calcium chloride [16,49].

159 To test solution toxicity, an aliquot (10 μ L) of each pool was placed under a glass
160 histological slide and an aliquot of the cryoprotectant solution (10 μ L) was added. Optical
161 microscopy indicated the presence/absence of motility [42,48]. When the solution was
162 not able to activate the sperm, an aliquot (10 μ L) of the activating solution was added to
163 the same slide and sperm motility was then observed again.

164 Samples were diluted at 1:4 (semen: freezing medium) ratio [15,9], placed into 0.5 ml
165 straws, identified and sealed with polyvinyl alcohol (PVA).

166 After solution stabilization (10 minutes), the straws containing the diluted semen were
167 packed in polyethylene racks and frozen at approximately -170 °C (-35.6 min⁻¹) [34],
168 using a dry-shipper nitrogen vapor canister (DS; Taylor-Wharton, model CP 300; - 170
169 °C), where they remained for three different freezing times, followed by transference to
170 a liquid nitrogen cylinder at -196 °C (Cryometal, model DS-18) and stored until analysis.
171 The tested DS freezing times were 15 minutes [40], 12 hours [55] and 24 hours [30].

172 For thawing, the straws were removed from the cryogenic tank (cryobank) (M.V.E.
173 Millennium, XC 20) and immediately submerged in a water bath at 60 °C for eight seconds
174 [35]. Aliquots were then separated for further analysis concerning sperm viability,
175 kinetics, motility duration and morphology.

176

177 **2.4 Fresh semen evaluations**

178 After collection, the semen was evaluated regarding seminal characteristics, namely
179 volume, pH, color, appearance, concentration, total motility, motility duration and sperm
180 vigor. Semen volume, color and appearance were assessed by direct observation in the
181 same graduated collection glass tubes.

182 The pH was measured with the aid of measuring strips (Merck, Germany). Sperm
183 concentration was measured using Neubauer hematimetric sperm counting methods

184 (sperm mL⁻¹) [59]. The semen analysis was conducted individually for each animal.
185 Motility assessments were subjectively estimated by observation under an optical
186 microscope, at 400x magnification, where the average percentage of motile cells in three
187 different fields was assigned and a value on a scale from 0 to 100% was assigned [42,58].
188 Cell activation was performed by mixing 5 µL semen with 40 µL of a 1% NaHCO₃
189 activator solution [30]. Motility duration was determined from semen dilution with the
190 activating solution until only 10% of the sperm remained motile, assessed with the aid of
191 a stopwatch.

192 The motility quality score (vigor) was subjective, classified using an arbitrary grading
193 system ranging from 0 (no movement) to 5 (rapidly swimming sperm) points [19,53].

194

195 **2.5 Fresh and post-thawed semen evaluation parameters**

196 **2.5.1 Sperm viability**

197 The eosin-nigrosin staining method using a 1:10:10 ratio (semen: eosin: nigrosine), was
198 chosen for this analysis, by counting 200 cells in distinct histological slide fields under
199 an optical microscope. Viability rates were assessed by counting cells displaying intact
200 membranes (alive), colorless, and cells displaying plasma membrane rupture (dead),
201 stained pink or red [31].

202

203 **2.5.2 Sperm motility**

204 Post-thawed semen motility analyses were performed objectively through a computerized
205 analysis system, using the SCA[®] software (Sperm class analyzer[®] - SCA, 2005,
206 Microptics, S.L., version 3.2.0).

207 A 10 µL thawed semen aliquot was mixed with 300 µL of the NaHCO₃ 1% activator
208 solution in an eppendorff microtube. Immediately after activation, 2 µL were removed,
209 placed in a Mackler hematimetric chamber (10 µm depth) and observed under a phase
210 contrast optical microscope (Nikon Eclipse E200[®], Tokyo, Japan) at 20 diopter
211 magnification, with a yellow filter at the pH1 position, coupled to a camcorder (Blaster
212 Vision Technologies[®] A602FC, Ahrensburg, Germany) that generates 25 images per
213 second, used to calculate the motility parameters. Video recording began 10 seconds after
214 activation. Images (n = 25) were analyzed using the standard fish setup available in the
215 Sperm Class Analyzer software (SCA[®], Microptics, Version 5.1 SL, Barcelona, Spain).
216 The following sperm kinetics parameters were evaluated: total motility (TM, %),
217 progressive motility (PM, %). Approximately 500 sperm/field were analyzed.

218 Motility duration (MT, seconds) of the fresh and thawed semen were determined with the
219 aid of a stopwatch, beginning at semen homogenization with the activating solution until
220 90% of the sperm remained immobile.

221

222 **2.5.3 Post-thawed morphological sperm cell changes**

223 A 10 μL aliquot of thawed semen was diluted in 990 μL of a formaldehyde citrate
224 solution. Then, a 10 μL fraction of the fixed sample was deposited on a histological slide
225 and covered with a coverslip. The analysis was carried out using a phase contrast optical
226 microscope (Nikon Eclipse Ci-S, China) at 100x, and the morphological alterations of
227 100 spermatozoa focused in distinct fields along the slide were assessed.

228 The following morphological sperm cell changes for semen head, midpiece and tail were
229 observed, according to Felizardo et al. [15]: head (microcephalic, macrocephalic,
230 degenerated, normal isolated), midpiece (proximal drop) and tail (fractured, strongly
231 coiled, degenerated, isolated, slightly bent and with a distal drop).

232

233 **2.5.4 Fertilization rate**

234 The reproduction induction method was performed by animal hypophysation, according
235 to the methodology adopted at the CEMIG Volta Grande Fish Farming Station. For five
236 females, a prior dose of 0.25 mg kg^{-1} of fish was applied, followed by a preparatory dose
237 of 0.5 mg kg^{-1} and, finally, a 5 mg kg^{-1} dose. Only three females responded to hormonal
238 induction. For males, a 5 mg kg^{-1} dose was used along with the same final female dose.
239 One straw from each treatment was thawed and used for fertilization. A 100 μL aliquot
240 of thawed sperm from each straw (n=5 pools) was used to fertilize 0.1 g of oocytes
241 (n=100) from three females separately (n=3), representing 5.88×10^8 sperm cells: 100
242 oocytes (for all treatments). Fertilization was initiated by adding 10 mL of the semen
243 activator 1% NaHCO_3 solution [30] to the semen and oocytes. The eggs were then
244 transferred to experimental incubators made of PVC (100 mm in diameter) with fine mesh
245 (400 μm), placed in concrete tanks with running water at 28 $^\circ\text{C}$.

246 To estimate the fertilization rate, two individual samples were taken from each 250
247 incubator and about 100 eggs were counted under a binocular stereomicroscope.

248

249 **2.6 Statistical analyses**

250 A completely randomized design with five replications (pools from three fish) and nine
251 treatments arranged in a 3 x 3 factorial structure (concentrations: 0, 1 and 2 mmol L^{-1}

252 melatonin x freezing times: 15 min, 12 h and 24 h) was applied. Data were analyzed using
 253 the R program and expressed as mean and standard deviation. The Shapiro-Wilks test was
 254 used to test data normality, followed by an analysis of variance (one-way ANOVA), and
 255 means were compared by the Tukey test when a significant effect was found ($p < 0.05$).

256

257 3 RESULTS

258 3.1 Fresh semen characteristics

259 The evaluated parameters regarding fresh semen characterization are presented in Table
 260 1.

261 **Table 1** – Fresh *Brycon orbignyanus* sperm features (n= 15 males; mean \pm standard
 262 deviation) after hypophysation treatment.

Parameters	Observed values
Volume (mL) *	7.6 \pm 1.1
Sperm concentration (sperm/mL) *	5.88 \pm 1.2 x 10 ⁹
semen pH *	8.2 \pm 0.32
Total Motility (%) *	94 \pm 5.48
Vigor*	4.0 \pm 0.82
Motility Duration (seconds) *	117.2 \pm 51.4

263 * Results are expressed as means \pm standard deviation.

264

265 3.2 Sperm viability

266 Sperm **viability** results are presented in Table 2. No significant interactions
 267 between the solutions and the tested **freezing times** were observed. However, decreased
 268 intact plasma membrane sperm rates were noted for M1 ($p < 0.05$).

269

270 **Table 2 - Intact plasma membrane sperm rates (%; mean \pm standard deviation) in fresh
 271 and thawed *B. orbignyanus* semen (n=5 pools) after different treatments, for the control
 272 solution, 1 mmol L⁻¹ melatonin (M1) and 2 mmol L⁻¹ melatonin (M2)**

	Fresh	Control	M1	M2
Means \pm SD (%) *	89.7 \pm 3.4 a	88.6 \pm 2.7 a	81.5 \pm 4.3 b	85.2 \pm 2.8 a

273 * Results are expressed as means \pm standard deviation. Different letters indicate significant statistical
 274 difference ($p < 0.05$).

275

276 3.3 Sperm motility

277 Sperm motility results are presented in Table 3. No significant interactions between the

278 solutions and the tested **freezing times** were observed. However, a statistically significant
279 difference ($p < 0.05$) was observed regarding motility duration (TM) and total motility
280 (MT) parameters between the control and M2 treatments, and for progressive motility
281 (MP) between the tested solutions and the control treatment.

282 Table 3 - Total motility (TM, %), motility duration (MT, seconds), and progressive motility (PM, %) (mean \pm standard deviation) after different
 283 291 treatments, for the control solution, 1 mmol L⁻¹ melatonin (M1) and 2 mmol L⁻¹ melatonin (M2) of thawed *Brycon orbignyianus* semen (n=5
 284 pools).

Treatment									
p1*	C			M1			M2		
	T1	T2	T3	T1	T2	T3	T1	T2	T3
TM	21.40 \pm 4.62	25.20 \pm 6.63	86.40 \pm 14.91	59.60 \pm 10.69	71.60 \pm 23.17	64.80 \pm 18.13	76.00 \pm 16.28	81.60 \pm 6.07	95.00 \pm 12.27
MT	18.04 \pm 3.63	38.86 \pm 10.51	39.54 \pm 4.49	42.56 \pm 5.69	56.04 \pm 17.95	43.34 \pm 12.11	56.20 \pm 15.48	56.18 \pm 5.53	81.50 \pm 9.59
PM	5.26 \pm 1.71	3.56 \pm 1.75	8.56 \pm 3.65	11.26 \pm 2.84	15.29 \pm 6.20	13.96 \pm 4.12	15.29 \pm 5.31	11.30 \pm 2.98	24.44 \pm 4.31

p1*	Solution			p1*	Freezing time		
	C	M1	M2		T1	T2	T3
TM	44.33 \pm 9.53c	65.33 \pm 9.75b	84.20 \pm 6.90a	TM	52.33 \pm 8.69b	49.47 \pm 10.10b	82.07 \pm 8.85a
MT	32.14 \pm 4.56c	47.31 \pm 7.10b	64.62 \pm 6.68a	MT	38.93 \pm 6.70	50.36 \pm 6.99	54.79 \pm 7.09
PM	5.79 \pm 1.46b	13.48 \pm 2.50a	17.00 \pm 2.73a	PM	10.60 \pm 2.22	10.03 \pm 2.55	15.65 \pm 2.78

285 * Results are expressed as means \pm standard deviation. Means followed by the same letters in the same line do not differ from each other by the Tukey test at a 5% probability.

286 ¹Parameter

287 **3.4 Morphological post-thawed sperm cell changes**

288 No significant interactions between the assessed solutions and tested **freezing times** were
289 noted, although a statistically significant difference ($p < 0.05$) was observed between
290 solutions (Table 4).

291

292 Table 4 – Comparison of head, midpiece and tail alterations (mean \pm SD, %) of fresh *B.*
293 *orbignyianus* semen and semen cryopreserved without melatonin (Control) or
294 supplemented with 1 mmol L⁻¹ (M1) and 2 mmol L⁻¹ of melatonin (M2) (n= 5 pools).

Treatment	Head	Midpiece	Tail	Total
Fresh	2.1 \pm 0.8 a	0.0 \pm 0.0 a	18.6 \pm 2.3 a	20.7 \pm 3.6 a
Control	12.3 \pm 1.2 b	0.9 \pm 0.1 a	44.2 \pm 12.5 b	57.4 \pm 5.9 b
M1	4.7 \pm 1.7 a	0.2 \pm 0.1 a	38.2 \pm 9.5 b	43.1 \pm 13.2 c
M2	3.7 \pm 0.6 a	0.0 \pm 0.0 a	36.6 \pm 14.8 b	40.3 \pm 11.4 c

295 Means followed by the same letters in the same column do not differ from each other by the Tukey test at
296 a 5% probability.

297

298 **3.5 Fertilization rate**

299 Fertilization rates were relatively low, never exceeding 8.4% of fertilized oocytes. No
300 significant effect on interactions between freezing time and solution was noted, while
301 difference ($p < 0.05$) between solutions for each time were observed. The highest
302 fertilization rates were noted in M2 at a freezing time of 15 minutes and 12 hours
303 maintenance in the dry shipper. The lowest rates were found in the control treatment at
304 all tested times. M1 presented better rates than the control treatment, but remained
305 constant throughout the evaluated times (Table 5).

306

307 Table 5 - Fertilization (mean \pm standard deviation) rates obtained with *B. orbignyianus*
308 fresh and thawed semen after different treatments, for the control, 1 mmol L⁻¹
309 melatonin(M1) and 2 mmol L⁻¹ melatonin (M2) at different freezing times (T1: 15
310 minutes, T2: 12 hours and T3: 24 hours). Semen (n=5 pools) was used to separately
311 fertilize female oocytes (n=3).

312

313

314

315

Treatment	T1	T2	T3
Control	1.61±0.25% a	1.06±0.84% a	1.62±0.32% a
M1	5.78± 1.21% b	5.74±2.14% b	5.12±1.65% b
M2	6.16±1.87% b	8.40±2.54% b	3.94±1.12% b

316 Results are expressed as means ± standard deviation. Different letters indicate significant statistical
317 difference (p <0.05).

318

319 4 DISCUSSION

320 Determining the qualitative aspects of fresh semen prior to freezing becomes an important
321 issue for semen biotechnology, as this can predict the success of stored material after
322 thawing. The fresh semen parameters observed herein are in agreement with those
323 reported in the literature [20,30,35,58]. The *Brycon* genus exhibits relatively high seminal
324 volumes and low sperm concentrations compared to other species, such as *P. lineatus*,
325 mainly after hormonal induction [18,38,37]. However, the volume reported by Oliveira et
326 al. [40] was lower compared to the present study, which may be due to the fact that the
327 authors did not perform hormone induction in males, as this technique can be used to
328 increase the volume of extruded semen [37]. The sperm concentration values in the
329 present study are close to those reported by Maria et al. [30] for *B. orbignyanus*, and
330 Murgas et al. [34] for the same species.

331 The change in the intracellular pH of sperm cells at activation is dependent on the pH of
332 the diluent medium [43]. Lahnsteiner et al. [26] reported a significant relationship
333 between semen pH and motile sperm in *Alburnus alburnus* (Ciprinidae), suggesting that
334 this parameter is an important seminal plasma characteristic and may influence sperm
335 motility potential. In the present study, the pH values for *B. orbignyanus* semen are
336 similar to those reported by Viveiros et al. [58] for *B. orbignyanus* (8.2 to 8.3).

337 One of the main requirements to consider regarding fish sperm quality is sperm motility
338 [1,32], which can be influenced by a number of factors, such as temperature, analysis
339 conditions, management and donor stress. The semen motility values found in this study
340 are in agreement with those reported by other authors for the species *B. orbignyanus*
341 [30,36,15]. The subjectively evaluated parameter that characterizes the speed at which
342 sperm move is termed sperm vigor, an important fish semen condition indicator when
343 assessed along with motility [11,56,19,53]. In the present study, this value was much
344 higher than those reported by other authors for other rheophilic species, such as 2.93 in

345 *Leporinus elongatus* [53] and 3.92 in *P. mesopotamicus* [52], but corroborate the value
346 reported by Viveiros et al. [57], of 5.0, for *B. orbignyana*.

347 Sperm viability is a required analysis concerning freezing protocols, as it is an plasma
348 membrane integrity indicator. In this study, a significant difference was found only
349 between the tested solutions. The highest intact plasma membrane sperm rates were found
350 in fresh semen samples, as well as in control solutions and the medium containing 2 mM
351 melatonin. The values found in the present study are consistent with those reported by
352 other authors, such as 82% in *Brycon henni* [45] and in other rheophilic species, as well
353 as values between 48% and 70% using dry shippers [55] without the use of melatonin in
354 the tested freezing solutions.

355 When assessing rabbit semen, Zhu et al. [60] observed that the addition of 0.1 mM
356 melatonin improved sperm motility, membrane integrity, acrosome integrity, and
357 mitochondrial membrane potential during cryopreservation or in an *in vitro* H₂O₂-induced
358 oxidative stress model. These last authors indicated the melatonin protects sperm from
359 ROS-induced cryo-damage through activating AMPK phosphorylation to enhance
360 antioxidative defenses and its direct anti-oxidative capacity. As we will emphasize during
361 this discussion when evaluating melatonin functions and its beneficial effects pointed out
362 in the literature, it is possible that this indolamine contributed to the high motility rates
363 and fertilization parameters observed in solutions containing melatonin.

364 Motility is a sperm quality criterion that allows for the assessment of freezing
365 effectiveness. After thawing, sperm kinetics parameters were evaluated. Although no
366 significant difference was observed between the melatonin-containing solutions (M1 and
367 M2), the solution containing the highest melatonin concentration resulted in higher values
368 for all the assessed three parameters, demonstrating that the cryoprotectant used in this
369 study in conjunction with melatonin exerted a positive influence when compared to the
370 control solution.

371 Assis et al. [4] evaluated total *P. lineatus* semen motility using different melatonin
372 concentrations (1, 2 and 3 mM) and observed total motility means of over 60.4% for the
373 treatments and for the control solution, except for the solution containing 3 mM melatonin,
374 determined as 30%. The authors concluded that melatonin addition to the cryoprotectant
375 solution did not alter motility, morphology or fertilization parameters for the studied
376 species. In contrast, the results of the present study demonstrate a positive effect for *B.*
377 *orbignyana* semen, as has been reported for mammalian species. Pariz et al. [41], when
378 evaluating the protective and stimulating effect of supplementation with melatonin and

379 caffeine (2 mmol L⁻¹) on the functional characteristics of human sperm before and after
380 freezing, observed a significant increase in progressive motility ($9.49 \pm 8.28\%$, $13.27 \pm$
381 2.62% for the melatonin and caffeine groups, respectively, compared to $7.50 \pm 2.71\%$ for
382 the control group. These differences can be explained by species- specific individual
383 differences and the different methods/challenges adopted for the freezing process.
384 Generally, motility duration is a trade-off between the level of energy stocks possessed
385 by a cell and the osmotic damage process experienced by this cell [12]. The observed TM
386 value in the M2 solution was of over 60%, with the longest motility duration among the
387 assessed solutions, indicating that sperm under these conditions is able to remain motile
388 for longer periods compared to the other treatments.

389 The observed progressivity was considerably lower in the control treatment compared to
390 the melatonin treatments, whose values observed herein were higher than those reported
391 by Atencio-Garcia et al. [6] for cryopreserved *B. moorei* semen ($7.1 \pm 4.6\%$). In
392 contrast, Pineda-Santis [45] reported values much higher than those observed herein (52
393 to 62%) for cryopreserved *B. henni* semen with dimethylformamide, dimethylsulfoxide
394 and ethylenglycol, respectively. These authors used the CASA system to evaluate sperm
395 and water as a semen activator.

396 Another aspect to be evaluated consists of the different melatonin concentrations assessed
397 in the literature. Deng et al. [13] reported that 0.001 mmol L⁻¹ and 1 mmol L⁻¹ lead to
398 adverse effects on thawed human sperm viability. Another study reported that 0.01 mmol
399 L⁻¹ melatonin was the most effective concentration to protect human spermatozoa from
400 cryopreservation damage [25]. It is likely that not all melatonin concentrations can
401 improve sperm cryopreservation function. Most of the findings reported herein follow
402 literature parameters and can be considered good reproductive rates for a reproductive
403 system that acts in the development of *B. orbignyana* semen banks.

404 The melatonin-containing solutions led to the lowest sperm cell abnormality rates when
405 compared to the control solution. Sperm cell morphology evaluations are highly related
406 to the fertilizing potential of sperm cells, since cell structure integrity is essential for an
407 adequate performance regarding this function, explaining sperm motility reduction most
408 of the time, and, consequently, loss of oocyte fertilizing capacity [53].

409 The mean rates of total morphological alterations concerning the assessed melatonin
410 solution samples were of less than 50%. According to Miliorini et al. [34], semen with up
411 to 50% of abnormal cells is considered suitable for use in fertilization processes,
412 considering that larger semen volumes should be used under these conditions when

413 compared to fresh semen fertilization. The most frequently occurring morphological
414 alterations were “coiled tail”, “isolated tail” and “isolated head”, all of which make it
415 difficult for sperm cells to move and may seriously compromise fertilization rates.

416 Regarding fertilization, higher values than those reported herein have been reported by
417 other authors for the same species, as well as in other rheophilic species, such as *B.*
418 *orbignyana* (45%) [17] and *P. lineatus* ($59.01 \pm 25.69\%$) [19]. One hypothesis to explain
419 the observed low fertilization rates may be some of the noted morphological sperm cell
420 changes, which may impair sperm motility. However, all melatonin treatments resulted
421 in higher fertilization rates compared to the control treatment. Cryopreservation leads to
422 ROS formation, which in turn compromises fertility and sperm parameters, among other
423 functions [13]. Li et al. [28] demonstrated that sperm preservation processes
424 (cryopreservation or short-term freezing) induce higher lipid peroxidation levels in
425 common carp. ROS are formed due to the low amounts of antioxidants and the high
426 concentration of polyunsaturated fatty acids in the plasma membrane [7]. Studies
427 assessing melatonin in fish semen cryopreservation are scarce, but a hypothesis
428 concerning this positive effect would be membrane stability caused by melatonin in
429 controlling ROS production during cryopreservation. Melatonin is an antioxidant capable
430 of sequestering highly reactive free radicals, neutralizing the hydroxyl radical. However,
431 further studies are required to determine oxidative stress markers (lipid peroxidation or
432 total antioxidant status, for example) under the conditions in which this assessment was
433 conducted to confirm this hypothesis.

434

435 **4 CONCLUSIONS**

436 The addition of melatonin at 2 mmol L^{-1} associated with the cryoprotectant methylglycol
437 in the freezing solution improves *B. orbignyana* sperm quality regarding sperm kinetics,
438 while the tested freezing times did not influence the quality of thawed semen.

439

440 **CONFLICTS OF INTEREST**

441 The authors declare that they have no competing financial interests.

442

443 **ACKNOWLEDGMENTS**

444 The authors would like to thank Flavio H. Siqueira and Manoel V. Oliveira (Estação de
445 Piscicultura da Usina Hidrelétrica da CEMIG) for providing the broodstock and team

446 accommodation, Gilson A. Azarias and Jailson M. Silva (Estação de Piscicultura da Usina
447 Hidrelétrica da CEMIG) for assistance during animal manipulation; Conselho Nacional
448 de Desenvolvimento Científico e Tecnológico-CNPq (Processo:456 304940/2014-3),
449 FAPEMIG and FUNDECC for the financial support of this project and CEMIG for
450 providing the fish and facilities used in this study. The authors would also like to thank
451 the Universidade Federal de Lavras Biotério Multiusuário team.

452

453 REFERENCES

454

455 [1] S.M.H. Alavi, J. Cosson. Sperm motility in fishes. I. Effects of temperature and pH:
456 A review, *Cell Biology International*, 2005. 29: p. 101–110.

457

458 [2] F.Y. Ashikaga, M. L. Orsi, C. Oliveira, J.A. Senhorini, F. Foresti. The
459 endangered species *Brycon orbignyanus*: Genetic analysis and definition of priority areas
460 for conservation. *Environmental Biology of Fishes*, 2015. 98: p. 1845–1855.

461

462 [3] I. Ashrafi, H. Kohram, F.F. Ardabili. Antioxidative effects of melatonin on kinetics,
463 microscopic and oxidative parameters of cryopreserved bull spermatozoa, *Animal
464 Reproduction Science*, 2013. 139: p. 25–30.

465

466 [4] I.L. Assis, P.C. Palhares, G.J. Machado, J.G.S. Souza, T.S. França, V.O. Felizardo,
467 L.D.S. Murgas. Effect of Melatonin on Cryopreserved Sperm of *Prochilodus lineatus*
468 (Characiformes), *Cryo-Letters*, 2019. 40: p. 152–158.

469

470 [5] J.F. Asturiano, E. Cabrita, Á. Horváth. Progress, challenges and perspectives on fish
471 gamete cryopreservation: A mini-review, *General and Comparative Endocrinology*, 2017.
472 245: p. 69–76.

473

474 [6] V.J. Atencio García, M.D. Longas, C.M. Prieto, M. Prieto-Guevara., J. Espinosa-
475 Araujo. Crioconservación de semen de dorada *Brycon moorei* con
476 dimetilsulfóxido, *Revista Colombiana de Biotecnología*, 2017. 19: p. 87–94.

477

478 [7] J. Beirão, L. Zilli, S. Vilella, E. Cabrita, C. Fernández-Díez, R. Schiavone,
479 M.P. Herráez. Fatty acid composition of the head membrane and flagella affects *Sparus
480 aurata* sperm quality, *Journal of Applied Ichthyology*, 2012. 28: p. 1017–1019.

481

482 [8] E. Cabrita, S. Martínez-Páramo, P.J. Gavaia, M.F. Riesco, D.G. Valcarce,
483 C. Sarasquete, M.P. Herráez, V. Robles. Factors enhancing fish sperm quality and
484 emerging tools for sperm analysis, *Aquaculture*, 2014. 432: p. 389–401.

485

486 [9] J. Carolsfeld, H.P. Godinho, E. Zaniboni Filho, B.J. Harvey. Cryopreservation of
487 sperm in Brazilian migratory fish conservation, *Journal of Fish Biology*, 2003. 63: p. 472–
488 486.

489

- 490 [10] B.B. Chapman, K. Hulthén, J. Brodersen, P.A. Nilsson, C. Skov, L.A. Hansson, C.
491 Brönmark. Partial migration in fishes: Causes and consequences, *Journal of Fish Biology*,
492 2012. 81: p. 456–478.
- 493
- 494 [11] J. Cosson, C. Dreanno, R. Billard, M. Suquet, C. Cibert. Regulation of
495 axonemalwave parameters of fish spermatozoa by ionic factors, in: C. Gagnon (Ed.),
496 Male Gametes from Basic Knowledge to Clinical Applications Cache River Press,
497 Montreal, 1999: pp.161–186.
- 498
- 499 [12] J. Cosson. Fish Sperm Physiology: Structure, Factors Regulating Motility, and
500 Motility Evaluation. *Biological Research in Aquatic Science*, Yusuf Bozkurt,
501 IntechOpen, 2020. DOI: 10.5772/intechopen.85139.
- 502
- 503 [13] S.L. Deng, T.C. Sun, K. Yu, Z.P. Wang, B.L. Zhang, Y. Zhang, X.X. Wang,
504 Z.X. Lian, Y.X. Liu. Melatonin reduces oxidative damage and upregulates heat shock
505 protein90 expression in cryopreserved human semen. *Free Radical Biology & Medicine*,
506 2017.113: p. 347–354.
- 507
- 508 [14] I.M. Di Chiacchio, I.L.G. Almeida, M.C. Leal, A.T.M. Viveiros. Sperm quality and
509 its freezing ability throughout the spawning season in *Prochilodus lineatus* and *Brycon*
510 *orbignyanus*, *Theriogenology*, 2017. 90: p. 284–288.
- 511
- 512 [15] V.O. Felizardo, C.C.V. Melo, L.D.S. Murgas, E.S.A., R.D. Navarro, R.T.F. Freitas.
513 Optimization of artificial propagation in piracanjuba fish *Brycon orbignyanus* using
514 cryopreserved semen, *CryoLetters*, 2016. 37: p. 330–334.
- 515
- 516 [16] V.O. Felizardo, L.D.S. Murgas, R.D. Navarro, A.C.S. Gonçalves, M.S. Paulino. 508
517 Osmolaridade e taxa de diluição na ativação do sêmen criopreservado de
518 *Prochilodus lineatus*, *Archivos de Zootecnia*, 2011. 60: p. 1255–1262.
- 519
- 520 [17] V.O. Felizardo, R.A. Mello, L.D.S. Murgas, E.S. Andrade, M.M Drumond,
521 P.V. Rosa, Effect of cryopreservant combinations on the motility and morphology of
522 curimba (*Prochilodus lineatus*) sperm, *Animal Reproduction Science*, 2010. 122: p. 259–
523 263.
- 524
- 525 [18] T.S. França, N.C. Motta, R.C. Egger, A.V. Oliveira, L.D.S. Murgas. Impact of
526 activation solutions on fresh and frozen-thawed sperm motility and fertilization success
527 for two species of migratory freshwater fishes, *Theriogenology*, 2020. 149: p. 6-15.
- 528
- 529 [19] J.M. Galo, D.P. Streit-Junior, C.A. Oliveira, J.P. Povh, D.C. Fornari, M. Digmayer,
530 R.P. Ribeiro. Quality of fresh and cryopreserved semen and their influence on the rates
531 of fertilization, hatching and quality of the larvae of *Piaractus mesopotamicus*, *Brazilian*
532 *Journal of Biology*, 2019. 79: p. 438–445.
- 533
- 534 [20] J.M. Galo, D.P. Streit-Junior, R.N. Sirol, R.P. Ribeiro, M. Digmayer,
535 V.X.L. Andrade, A.R. Ebert. Anormalidades espermáticas de piracanjuba *Brycon*

536 *orbignyanus* (Valenciennes, 1849) após a criopreservação, Brazilian Journal of Biology,
537 2011. 71: p.693–699.
538

539 [21] A.C. Gonçalves, A. Nascimento, A. Costa, M. Leal, A.T. Viveiros. Initiation and
540 suppression of sperm motility is osmolality dependent in two South American fish
541 species: streaked prochilod (*Prochilodus lineatus*) and Piracanjuba (*Bryconorbignyanus*),
542 Animal Reproduction, 2013. 10: p. 62–70.
543

544 [22] B. Harvey, J. Carolsfeld. Preservation of sperm. in B. Harvey, J. Carolsfeld (Eds.),
545 Induced breeding in tropical fish culture. Ottawa, ON, Canada: International
546 Development Research Centre, 1993: 144p.
547

548 [23] Y. Horokhovatskyi, M. Rodina, H. D. Asyabar, S. Boryshpolets, B. Dzyuba.
549 Consequences of uncontrolled cooling during sterlet (*Acipenser ruthenus*) sperm
550 cryopreservation on post-thaw motility and fertilizing ability, Theriogenology, 2017.
551 95:p. 89–95.
552

553 [24] G. Izadpanah, A. Zare-Shahneh, M. Zhandi, I. Yousefian, M. Emamverdi. Melatonin
554 has a beneficial effect on stallion sperm quality in cool condition, Journal of Equine
555 Veterinary Science, 2015. 35: p. 555–559.
556

557 [25] M.H Karimfar, F. Niazvand, K. Haghani, S. Ghafourian, R. Shirazi, S. Bakhtiyari.
558 The protective effects of melatonin against cryopreservation-induced oxidative stress
559 in human sperm. International Journal of Immunopathology and Pharmacology, 2015.
560 28:p. 69–76.
561

562 [26] F. Lahnsteiner, B. Berger, T. Weismann, R.A. Patzner. Motility of spermatozoa of
563 *Alburnus alburnus* (Cyprinidae) and its relationship to seminal plasma composition and
564 sperm metabolism, Fish Physiology and Biochemistry, 1996. 15: p. 167–179.
565

566 [27] F.C.T. Lima. A revision of the cis-andean species of the genus *Brycon* Müller
567 & Troschel (Characiformes: Characidae). Zootaxa, 2017. 4222: p. 001–189.
568

569 [28] P. Li, Z.H. Li, B. Dzyuba, M. Hulak, M. Rodina, O. Linhart. Evaluating the impacts
570 of osmotic and oxidative stress on common carp (*Cyprinus carpio* L.) sperm caused by
571 cryopreservation techniques, Biology of Reproduction, 2010. 83: p. 852–858.
572

573 [29] J.T. Lopes, C.S.B. Salmito-Vanderley, P.S. Almeida-Monteiro. Presença de
574 antioxidantes no sêmen de teleósteos e sua utilização na suplementação de meios
575 descongelamento seminal, Revista Brasileira de Reprodução Animal, 2016. 40: p. 29–34.
576

577 [30] A.N. Maria, A.T.M. Viveiros, R.T.F. Freitas, A.V. Oliveira. Extenders and
578 cryoprotectants for cooling and freezing of piracanjuba (*Brycon orbignyanus*) semen, an
579 endangered Brazilian teleost fish, Aquaculture. 2006. 260: p. 298–306.
580

581 [31] A.N. Maria, H.C. Azevedo, J.P. Santos, P.C.F. Carneiro. Hormonal induction and
582 semen characteristics of tambaqui *Colossoma macropomum*, Zygote, 2012. 20: p. 39–43.

583

584 [32] S. Martínez-Páramo, Á. Horváth, C. Labbé, T. Zhang, V. Robles, P. Herráez,
585 M.Suquet, S. Adams, A. Viveiros, T.R. Tiersch, E. Cabrita. Cryobanking of aquatic
586 species, *Aquaculture*, 2017. 472: p. 156–177.

587

588 [33] S. Martínez-Páramo, P. Diogo, M.T. Dinis, F. Soares, C. Sarasquete, E. Cabrita.
589 Effect of two sulfur-containing amino acids, taurine and hypotaurine in European sea bass
590 (*Dicentrarchus labrax*) sperm cryopreservation, *Cryobiology*, 2013. 66: p. 333–338.

591

592 [34] A.B. Miliorini, L.D.S. Murgas, P.V. Rosa, G. Oberlender, G.J.M. Pereira, D.V. Da
593 Costa. A morphological classification proposal for curimba (*Prochilodus lineatus*) sperm
594 damages after cryopreservation, *Aquaculture Research*, 2011. 4: p.2 177–187.

595

596 [35] L.D.S. Murgas, A.B. Miliorini, R.T. Franciscatto, A.N. Maria. Viabilidade
597 espermática do sêmen de piracanjuba (*Brycon orbignyanus*) resfriado a 4°C, *Revista*
598 *Brasileira de Zootecnia*, 2004. 33: p. 1361–1365.

599

600 [36] L.D.S. Murgas, R.T. Franciscatto, A.G.O. Santos. Avaliação espermática pós-
601 descongelamento em Piracanjuba (*Brycon orbignyanus*, Valenciennes, 1849), *Revista*
602 *Brasileira de Zootecnia*, 2003. 32: p. 1810–1814.

603

604 [37] C.C. Mylonas, N.J. Duncan, J.F. Asturiano. Hormonal manipulations for the
605 enhancement of sperm production in cultured fish and evaluation of sperm quality.
606 *Aquaculture*, 2017. 472: p. 21–44.

607

608 [38] A. Ninhaus-Silveira, F. Foresti, R. Veríssimo-Silveira, J.A. Senhorini. Seminal
609 analysis, cryogenic preservation, and fertility in matrinxã fish, *Brycon cephalus*
610 (Günther,1869), *Brazilian Archives of Biology and Technology*, 2006. 49: p. 651–659.

611

612 [39] D.J. Oliveira, F.Y. Ashikaga, F. Foresti, J.A. Senhorini. Conservation Status of the
613 “Piracanjuba” *Brycon orbignyanus* (Valenciennes, 1850) (Characiformes, Bryconidae):
614 Basis for Management Programs, *Biodiversidade Brasileira*, 2017. 7: p. 18–33.

615

616 [40] D.J. Oliveira, F.Y. Ashikaga, F. Foresti, J.A. Senhorini. Indução a reprodução
617 artificial e caracterização espermática da *Piracanjuba brycon orbignyanus* (Bryconidae,
618 Characiformes), espécie em perigo de extinção. *Evolução e Conservação Da*
619 *Biodiversidade*. 2015. 5: p. 10.

620

621 [41] J.R. Pariz, C. Ranéa, R.A.C. Monteiro, D.P. Evenson, J.R. Drevet, J. Hallak.
622 Melatonin and Caffeine Supplementation Used, Respectively, as Protective and
623 Stimulating Agents in the Cryopreservation of Human Sperm Improves Survival,
624 Viability, and Motility after Thawing compared to Traditional TEST-Yolk Buffer,
625 *Oxidative Medicine and Cellular Longevity*, 2019. 2019: p. 1-10.

626

627 [42] D.A.J. Paula, L.D.S Murgas, T.F.D. Castro, I.L. Assis, R.V.R. Neto, S. Marcussi.
628 Effects of cooling rates on the quality of *Prochilodus lineatus* (Valenciennes,
629 1836)sperm, *Reproduction in Domestic Animals*, 2019. 54: p. 1034–1043.

630

631 [43] L. Pérez, V. Gallego, J.F. Asturiano. Intracellular pH regulation and sperm motility
632 in the European eel. *Theriogenology*, 2020. 145: p. 48–58.25

633

634 [44] P. Perumal, K. Vupru, K. Khate. Effect of addition of melatonin on the liquid storage
635 (5 °C) of mithun (*Bos frontalis*) semen, *International Journal of Zoology*, 2013.

636

637 [45] H. Pineda-Santis, J. Gómez-Oquendo, J. Montoya-Páez, O. Acevedo-Villa,
638 G. Restrepo-Betancur, V. Toro-Rendón. Crioconservación de semen y calidad
639 espermática en sabaleta *Brycon henni* (Pisces: Characidae), *Orinoquia*. 2015. 19: p. 166.

640

641 [46] R.J. Reiter. Melatonin: Lowering the high price of free radicals, *News in*
642 *Physiological Sciences*, 2000. 15: p. 246–250.

643

644 [47] E.G. Sanches, G.A.M. Tosta, J.J. Souza-Filho, Viabilidade econômica da produção
645 de formas jovens de bijupirá (*Rachycentron canadum*), *Boletim do Instituto de Pesca*,
646 2013. 39: p. 15–26.

647

648 [48] M.R.I. Sarder, M.F.M. Sarker, S.K. Saha. Cryopreservation of sperm of
649 anindigenous endangered fish species *Nandus nandus* (Hamilton, 1822) for ex-situ
650 conservation, *Cryobiology*, 2012. 65: 202–209.

651

652 [49] E. Shimoda, E., D.R. Andrade, M.V. Vidal Júnior, G.S. Yasui, J.F.S. Silva,
653 H.P. Godinho, G. Souza, Efeitos da osmolaridade sobre a motilidade espermática na
654 piabanha *Brycon insignis*, *Revista Ceres*, 2007. 54: p. 430–433.

655

656 [50] E.Z. Sousa, L.W.O. Jesus, W.A. Meireles, M.I. Borella, P.K.F.C. Bianchi, M.L.B
657 Salvadori, J.R. Kfoury Júnior. O desenvolvimento embrionário da Piapara,
658 *Leporinus elongatus* (Pisces, Anostomidae), utilizando técnicas de histologia,
659 microscopia eletrônica de varredura e imunológicas empregando marcadores ósseos,
660 *Pesquisa Veterinária Brasileira*, 2014. 34: p. 92–98.

661

662 [51] W.L. Souza, E.A. Moraes, J.M.S. Costa, P.H.F. Sousa, E.S. Lopes Junior,
663 R.P. Oliveira, R. Tonioli. Efeito de diferentes concentrações de melatonina em
664 espermatozoides de carneiros sobre estresse oxidativo após criopreservação, *Pesquisa*
665 *Veterinária Brasileira*, 2016. 36: p. 657–664.

666

667 [52] D.P. Streit, A.C. de Oliveira, R.P. Ribeiro, R.N. Sirol, G.V. de Moraes, J.M. Galo, M.
668 Digmayer. Motilidade, Vigor e patologias seminal *in natura* e pós criopreservação de
669 *Piaractus mesopotamicus*, *Boletim do Instituto de Pesca*, 2009. 35: p. 159–167.

670

671 [53] D.P. Streit, R.N. Sirol, R.P. Ribeiro, G.V. Moraes, L.D.M. Vargas, A.L. Watanabe.
672 Qualitative parameters of the piapara semen (*Leporinus elongatus* Valenciennes, 1850),
673 *Brazilian Journal of Biology*, 2008. 68: p. 373–377.

674

- 675 [54] P.F. Taitson, E. Chami, H.P. Godinho. Gene banking of the neotropical fish
676 *Leporinus obtusidens* (Valenciennes, 1836): A protocol to freeze its sperm in the field,
677 *Animal Reproduction Science*, 2008. 105: p. 283–291.
678
- 679 [55] A.S. Varela Junior, K.L. Goularte, J.P. Alves, F.A. Pereira, E.F. Silva, T.F. Cardoso,
680 R.D. Jardim, D.P. Streit Jr, C.D. Corcini. Methods of cryopreservation of Tambaqui
681 semen, *Colossoma macropomum*. *Animal Reproduction Science*, 2015. 157: p.71–77.
682
- 683 [56] E.L.M. Vermeirssen, C. Mazorra de Quero, R.J. Shields, B. Norberg, D.E. Kime, A.P.
684 Scott, Fertility and motility of sperm from Atlantic halibut (*Hippoglossus hippoglossus*)
685 in relation to dose and timing of gonadotrophin-releasing hormone agonist implant,
686 *Aquaculture*. 2004. 230: p. 547–567.
687
- 688 [57] A.T.M. Viveiros, A.C.S. Gonçalves, A.F. Nascimento, M.C. Leal. Fresh,
689 equilibrated and post-thaw sperm quality of *Brycon orbignyanus* (Valenciennes, 1850)
690 and *Prochilodus lineatus* (Valenciennes, 1837) treated with either salmon GnRH α and
691 domperidone or pituitary extract, *Neotropical Ichthyology*, 2015. 13: p. 157–164.
692
- 693 [58] A.T.M. Viveiros, I.M. Di Chiacchio, I.L.G. Almeida, M.C. Leal. Seminal plasma
694 features of *Prochilodus lineatus* and *Brycon orbignyanus* throughout two consecutive
695 spawning seasons, *Molecular Reproduction and Development*, 2019. 86: p. 776–785.
696
- 697 [59] S. Wirtz, P. Steinmann. Sperm characteristics in perch *Perca fluviatilis* L., *Journal of*
698 *Fish Biology*, 2006. 68: p. 1896–1902. [60] Z. Zhu, R. Li, Y. Lv, W. Zeng, Melatonin
699 protects rabbit spermatozoa from cryo-damage via decreasing oxidative stress,
700 *Cryobiology*. 2019. 88: p. 1–8.